

D2.4 Report on methods for measuring patient benefit-risk preferences in medical treatment

115966 – PREFER

Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessment during the Drug Life Cycle

[WP2 – Patient preference
elicitation issues and
approaches]

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Abstract

Background

Throughout the life cycle of medicinal products and medical devices, the role of patient preferences in medical development and regulatory decision-making is becoming more and more important. Consequently, the role of patient preference elicitation is also becoming more important. Medical decision making, especially in benefit-risk (B-R) assessment, has become more patient-centric, with patient preferences being one of the key components. However, there is no comprehensive, current overview of preference exploration and elicitation methods. The aim of this study was to identify and describe existing methods to assess patient preferences for medicinal products and devices.

Methods

We used a three-step approach to identify existing preference exploration (qualitative) and preference elicitation (quantitative) methods: 1) methods that were the focus of previous preference methods reviews, 2) systematic literature review, and 3) consultations of international preference study experts not affiliated with the PREFER project. The consultations served to comment on the existing list, suggest additional promising methods, if any, and to comment on the grouping of methods. For Step 1, we used the study of Ryan et al [5] and the Medical Device Innovation Consortium Patient Centered B-R Framework project [8] as a starting point. For Step 2, a systematic review was conducted in different scientific databases, searching for published English full text papers between 1980 and 2016. The search strategy focused on preference exploration and elicitation methods and preferences of patients, caregivers or caretakers for medicinal products and medical devices. Data extraction was done by two independent reviewers. For Step 3, international experts in the field of health preferences and/or medical decision making both affiliated and not affiliated with the PREFER project were consulted by e-mail or phone.

Results

We identified 32 preference exploration and elicitation methods that have been applied to the development of medicinal products and medical devices. Twenty-two methods were identified from two previous method reviews. In the systematic review, 12,136 papers were identified, of which 4,572 unique papers were screened on title and abstract. Using pre-specified exclusion criteria, 323 papers of interest were included, resulting in the identification of 18 preference elicitation methods, 5 of which were unidentified in Step 1. Lastly, from the consultations of international experts, the list of the methods identified were validated, four additional methods were identified and consensus was reached about grouping the methods.

Conclusion

In this study, 32 methods utilised to obtain insights into patient preferences were identified. Although all these methods can be used for medicinal products and medical devices, only 18 of the 32 had previously been applied to medicinal products and medical devices. These findings will serve as the starting point for PREFER task 2.6, in which the 32 methods will be appraised through specific criteria, and PREFER WP3, which will utilise selected methods in case studies. The results of task 2.4 and its subsequent uses in later tasks will help determine which of these methods are most promising to obtain insights into patient preferences to support decision-making throughout the lifecycle of medicinal products and medical devices.

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Introduction

There is an emerging consensus that the patient perspective should be incorporated within decisions in the medicinal product and medical device life cycle [1]. As such, taking the patient voice into consideration has not only become increasingly important for the companies that develop new medicinal products and medical devices, but also for the authorities that assess, regulate and decide which products and devices are effective, safe, well-tolerated, and cost-effective [2, 3]. However, there is little guidance on incorporating the patient perspective, and patient preferences in particular, into development, regulatory or reimbursement decision-making.

The PREFER ('Patient Preferences in Benefit and Risk Assessment during the Treatment Life Cycle') project was launched in 2016; a five-year project funded equally by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI; Europe's largest public-private initiative aiming to speed the development of better and safer medicines for patients) and by the pharmaceutical industry through EFPIA [4]. The main objective of PREFER is to strengthen patient-centric decision making by developing expert and evidence-based recommendations to guide different stakeholders (industry, regulatory authorities, HTA bodies, reimbursement agencies, academia, health care professionals and patient organisations) on how and when patient preference studies should be performed, and how preference study results can be used to inform decision-making.

PREFER consists of four different Work Packages (WP's). Each WP is composed by sub-tasks. WP 1 covers overall project management, dissemination and communication activities; WP 2 seeks to understand stakeholder concerns around the measurement and use of patient-preference studies, make recommendations about the methodologies to be used in case studies, and define criteria for how the case studies will be assessed; WP 3 will design, execute and evaluate the case studies; and WP 4 will develop recommendations that incorporate the lessons learned from the case studies.

One of the first important steps in WP 2 is to identify those methods that can be used to obtain insights into patient preferences (ffi. PREFER task 2.4). As described in the Methods section below, we classify the methods into two broad categories: preference exploration methods and preference elicitation methods. There are numerous methods of both types in the field of health preference research [5]. For example, we can distinguish between structured interviews vs. focus groups vs. the Delphi method preference exploration methods, stated preference vs. revealed preference elicitation methods and trade-off related vs. non-trade-off related methods [6, 7]. Ryan *et al.* in 2001 provided an overview of methods known at the time for eliciting public preferences for healthcare [5]. In addition, in 2015 the Medical Device Innovation Consortium (MDIC) public-private partnership conducted a project entitled "Patient Centered B-R. The project developed an overview of different preference elicitation methods as part of their framework for incorporating patient preferences into regulatory assessments of medical devices [8]. Although both studies made useful contributions, the study of Ryan *et al.* does not reflect methods developed since 2001, and the MDIC framework did not

include preference exploration methods and did not use a systematic approach of identifying preference elicitation methods.

Task 2.4 in PREFER aims to obtain a comprehensive, current overview of preference exploration and elicitation methods useful for medical treatments by means of a systematic review and expert consultations. This present report is organised as follows: the methods section describes the three-step approach used; the results reports the outcomes of each step, followed by discussion of results and conclusions. The annexes provide additional information on search terms and search strategy for the systematic literature review, the papers considered for the review, and brief definitions of each preference exploration and elicitation method included.

Methods

For this work, we used the definition of preference from the FDA and MDIC: Patient preferences are qualitative or quantitative assessments of the relative desirability or acceptability to patients of specified alternatives or choices among outcomes or other attributes that differ among alternative health interventions [9].

Within this study, we examined: Any method that enables gaining insight into patient (or caregiver or caretaker) preferences on the benefits, harms or other attributes of treatments that can potentially contribute to decision-making in drug or medical device development at any point in the medicinal product or medical device life cycle. This includes preference exploration methods, which we defined to be qualitative methods that collect descriptive data through participant or phenomenon observation, and examining the subjective experiences and decisions made by participants. We also examined preference elicitation methods, which we defined to be quantitative methods collecting quantifiable data that can be reported through statistical inferences or analysis. Of note, the line of demarcation between preference exploration and elicitation methods is not always clear. For example a preference exploration method can also contain (elements of) elicitation methods, and generally preference exploration methods are used to support application of a preference elicitation method. For this review we specifically included distinct methods that utilize trade-offs. Scale-related techniques that can merely be used as a component of an elicitation method, or decision-making frameworks that define a structured approach to decision making, including a step that uses one or more of these preference elicitation methods, were excluded in this review (see Results section).

In this study we used a three-step approach. First, we drafted an overview of preference exploration and elicitation methods in the areas of medicinal products and medical devices based on outcomes of previous related research, more specifically previous related preference methods reviews. Second, we conducted a systematic literature review to specifically identify methods applied to medicinal

products and medical devices. Third, we consulted experts for validation and confirmation of our results (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Three-step approach

Step 1: Outcomes of previous research

Based on the outcomes of Ryan *et al.* [5] and the MDIC framework report [8], we developed a list of possible relevant preference exploration and elicitation methods. We eliminated methods per our aim and definitions. More specifically, we excluded instruments specifically developed for the QALY framework (e.g. EQ-5D, HUI, SF-36). The identified methods served as a foundation for the systematic review (Step 2), and also provided a substantial list to which we were able to cross-check the results of the systematic review.

Step 2: Systematic literature review

To minimize the chances of missing methods that could be applied within the area of medicinal products and medical devices, we developed a search query with generally broad search terms. Nevertheless, due to practical constraints, we restricted our search terms to existing applications to medicinal products and medical devices; i.e., the search may miss methods that could be applied to medicinal products and medical devices but had not been applied to date (Table 1).

Search term group: Patient	Search term group: Preference	Search term group: Method	Search term group: Elicitation	Search term group: Drug/medical device
Patient	Preference	Method	Elicitation	Drug
Client	Acceptability	Methodology	Measuring	Pharmaceutical
Citizen	Utility	Technique	Determine	Medicine
Consumer	Desirability	Measurement	Explore	Medication
Public		Instrument		Medical device
General population		Tool		Medical instrument
		Measure		

Table 1. Overview search terms systematic literature review. At least one term from each column was necessary for inclusion.

We searched for papers from 1980 until 2016 in six scientific databases: Cochrane Library, Econlit, Embase, PubMed, PsycInfo and Scopus. The search query is presented in Annex I. We did not use indexed terms (e.g. MeSH terms) because this generated too many irrelevant results.

The systematic literature review included analyses of both technical/methodological and application studies. The review was conducted according to the guidelines of the Joanna Briggs Institute [10]. First, papers were screened for relevance based on the title and abstract. Second, if papers could not be excluded based on title or abstract, the papers were screened for relevance based on the full-text.

We included papers if they were:

- Focused on technical/methodological aspects of preference exploration and elicitation methods (including publications focused on reviews or protocols) or were related to an application study;
- Focused on medicinal products or medical devices;
- Focused on preferences of patients (or caregivers or caretakers) regarding medicinal products or medical devices;
- Published between 1980-2016;
- A full peer-reviewed text paper;
- Available in the English language.

Papers were excluded if, they were:

- Focused on preference exploration and elicitation methods specifically developed for an economic evaluation or for the QALY framework only.

Titles, abstracts and/or full-text papers were independently screened for eligibility by two reviewers

(VS and CW) as well as the date extraction. Differences were discussed between both reviewers to reach consensus. A third reviewer (JV or EBG) was consulted when consensus could not be reached.

Step 3: Expert consultation for validation and confirmation

To validate and confirm our outcomes from Step 1 and Step 2, international experts (n=24) in the field of health preferences and/or medical decision making were consulted. These experts were consulted via e-mail or phone, and acted on a volunteering basis without any compensation. The experts were from different continents and different and specialised expertise in health preferences and/or medical decision making.

The experts were consulted in two rounds. In the first round consulted experts included 13 scientists within PREFER WP2 and the PREFER Scientific Advisory Group members. The second round included 11 experts outside the PREFER consortium. In both rounds our aim was to reach consensus about whether the list of identified preference methods was correct and complete, and whether the grouping of the methods was acceptable. Regarding completeness, we encouraged the experts to add other promising preference methods we might have not identified.

There are many ways that the methods can be grouped. In our case we grouped the methods according to their methodological relationships and the similarities in their techniques, as this was the grouping that was most acceptable among the consulted (inter)national experts. The exploration methods were therefore grouped based on the number of participants a method utilizes in one session, while the elicitation methods were grouped based on the way the data is elicited. This grouping was not intended to be a formal lexicon, but primarily serves as a means to organize our results. Subsequent parts of the PREFER project may provide insights to help a researcher select one method over another. It is also important to mention that many of the methods we identified could be regarded as classes of methods with many variations of their own, and that the grouping of the methods we proposed in this report required that we established a decision rule to distinguish between groups of methods as is described in the Results section.

Results

In Step 1, 23 preference exploration and elicitation methods were identified. In Step 2, the systematic review identified 5 additional methods (see Annex II). In Step 3, international preference experts identified 4 additional methods. In total, 32 preference exploration and elicitation methods were identified (see Annex III for their descriptions). The following sections describe the results of each step in more detail.

Step 1: Outcomes of previous research

Through the examination of the preference methods reviews of Ryan *et al.* [5] and the MDIC [8], and after condensing and grouping several of their methods³, we identified 23 preference exploration and elicitation methods that were relevant to our objectives and aims. This included 9 preference exploration and 14 elicitation methods (Table 2). Brief descriptions for each method are given below. Annex III has more detailed descriptions and references for the methods.

Table 2. Methods identified through previous research by Ryan *et al.*[5] and/or the MDIC [8] that were relevant to PREFER objectives and aims

Preference exploration methods	Preference elicitation methods
Citizen's jury	Allocation of points
Complaints procedures	Analytic hierarchy process
Concept mapping	Best-worst scaling (Types 1, 2, 3)
Delphi method	Contingent valuation
Dyadic interview	Discrete choice experiment
Focus group discussion	Measure of value
Public meetings	Nominal group technique
(Semi)structured-individual interview	Person trade-off
In depth- individual interview	Qualitative discriminant process
	Standard gamble
	Swing weighting
	Threshold techniques
	Time trade-off
	Visual analogue scale

The preference exploration methods identified included **Citizens' juries** which consists of a group of individuals discussing issues on the basis of evidence provided by two trained moderators. **Complaints procedures** are systems in which stakeholders can register complaints in order to be investigated by experts. **Concept mapping** is a method that utilises small groups of participants responding to various topics or issues, while ensuring each respondent is given equal opportunity to express their opinions, and addressing other group dynamic issues. The **Delphi method** is a structured, iterative forecasting method involving a panel of experts who provide anonymous responses to questionnaires with the opportunity to revise their responses when the anonymous summary of response from the prior round are revealed. **Dyadic interviews** utilise two participants in a single interview, responding to open-ended questions asked by an interviewer to identify how a

³ For example, "random paired scenarios" mentioned in Ryan *et al.* [5] became absorbed into our broader category of "discrete choice experiment".

product, service or opportunity is perceived. **Focus groups** utilise a group of interacting individuals contributing information about a specific issue to identify how a product, service or opportunity is perceived. **Public meetings** gain public opinion on particular issues by allowing general members of the public to attend and voice their responses. **(Semi)structured individual interview** is an interview technique which allows new ideas to be brought up during the interview as a result of what the interviewee says in a semi-structured setting, whereas in the structured setting the interviewer does not bring up new ideas during the interview. **In depth-individual interview** conducts intensive discussions with a small number of respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular topic or theme, to gain a deeper understanding of this particular topic or theme.

The preference elicitation methods identified included **Allocation of points**, which involves asking respondents to rate their conditions on scales, while knowing the weights which they attach to different criteria, indicating the relative importance of particular areas of their lives. **Analytic hierarchy process (AHP)**, in which responders assess the relative importance of pairs of attributes (treatment endpoints, properties, criteria, items, objects, etc.) towards achieving a goal, and the comparisons are then used to compute a weight for each attribute. **Best-worst scaling (BWS) (Types 1, 2, 3)** involves respondents responding to surveys that include lists of attributes or treatment profiles, and being asked to indicate the best (or most appealing/important) and the worst (or least appealing/important) of them. There are three forms of BWS: Type 1, called the Object Case, shows a set of attributes that may not reflect the characteristics of any particular treatment, of which the respondent picks the best and worst; Type 2, called the Profile Case, in which the attributes collectively characterize a particular treatment profile, and again the respondent picks the best and worst (Type 1 and 2 can be regarded as ranking exercises); and Type 3, which shows three or more treatment profiles, and the respondent selects the best and worst profiles (this Type is very similar to a discrete choice experiment). **Discrete choice experiments (DCE)** utilise an attribute-based measure of benefit, during which individuals are offered a series of hypothetical choice situations (i.e., choice sets), from which they are asked to choose between two or more treatment profiles. There are numerous variants of both BWS and DCEs. **Measure of value (MoV)** is used to identify the optimal bundle of services to be provided given resource constraints. Individuals are asked to allocate a fixed amount of resources between different services. These allocations are analysed to identify the trade-offs individuals make and to identify the optimal bundle of services to be provided within the given resource constraints. **Nominal group technique (NGT)** is a group process that involves making decisions by vote and ranking responses given by members of the group. **Person trade-off (PTO)** evaluates the health effects of interventions, including the distribution of interventions, using persons as the equilibrating mechanism. **Qualitative discriminant process (QDP)** is a scoring and ranking process based on decision analysis technique, involving the definition of options in terms of qualitative categories, then deriving a numeric point estimate, and finally solving a maximization problem with given constraints. **Standard gamble (SG)** asks respondents to choose between a certain outcome and a gamble which may result in either a

better outcome with a probability p , or a worse outcome than the original with a probability $1-p$. **Swing weighting** is a method for setting the weights in which a decision-relevant range is specified for each attribute, and the impact of “swinging” the attribute through that entire range of values is assigned a weight relative to the impact of swinging the attribute with the largest weight. **(Probabilistic) Threshold techniques**, or probabilistic threshold techniques determine the maximal change in one attribute respondents are willing to accept to achieve a given change in another attribute. **Time trade-off (TTO)** presents individuals with a choice between living for a period in a specified, but less than perfect, state versus having a healthier life for a period of time, where time is varied until the respondent is indifferent between the alternatives. A **Visual Analogue Scale (VAS)** is a self-reporting device consisting of a line of predetermined length that separates extreme boundaries of the phenomenon being measured. **Contingent valuation** is an approach to determine the willingness-to-pay (WTP) based on the money that a participant is willing to forgo in order to have a commodity.

Step 2: Systematic literature review

The complete screening procedure is illustrated in Figure 2. The systematic review yielded 12,136 potentially relevant papers, of which 4,572 papers remained for screening on the basis of the title, abstract and/or full-text. This screening excluded 4,249 papers based on the exclusion criteria. In total, 323 papers were reviewed to identify preference elicitation and exploration methods (see all 323 papers/studies listed in Annex II).

The systematic review, spanning 36 years of literature showed an increase in the number of medicinal product and medical device patient preferences publications per year. The mean number of publications increased from 1.6 per year to 11.6 per year to 32.2 per year, for the periods 1980-2000, 2001-2010, and 2011-2016 respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Flow diagram of systematic literature review inclusion and exclusion process

Figure 3: Number of patient preference studies in area of medicinal products and medical devices per publication year

Based on these 323 papers, which included 5 systematic reviews, 18 technical and/or methodological papers, and 300 application studies, a total of 18 methods were identified (Table 3, see Annex III for their descriptions).

Table 3. Methods resulting from the systematic review

Preference Exploration Methods	Preference Elicitation Methods
Delphi method	Adaptive conjoint analysis
Focus groups	Analytic hierarchy process
(Semi) structured - individual interviews	Best-Worst Scaling (Types 1, 2, 3)
In depth - individual interviews	Contingent valuation
	Control preference scale
	Discrete choice experiment
	Outcome prioritization tool
	Person-trade off
	Repertory grid method
	Standard gamble
	Starting known efficacy
	(Probabilistic)Threshold techniques
	Time trade-off
	Visual analogue scale

The list of 18 methods was cross-checked with earlier research by Ryan *et al.* [5] and the MDIC [8]. Based on this cross-check, we identified 13 methods that were both in the review (Step 2) and the previous preference methods reviews (Step 1) (see Figure 4): **Analytic hierarchy process (AHP)** [eg. studies 139, 221], **Best-worst scaling (BWS) (Types 1, 2, 3)** [eg. studies 133, 300], **Contingent valuation** [eg. Studies 144, 148, 229], **Delphi method** [eg. studies 72, 165, 317], **Discrete choice experiments (DCE)** [eg. studies 19, 25, 26], **Focus groups** [e.g. studies 72, 165, 317], **Person trade-off (PTO)** [eg. study 298], **(Semi)structured individual - interviews** [eg. studies 65, 275], **Standard gamble (SG)** [eg. studies 195, 219, 281], **In depth - individual interviews** [eg. studies 9, 186], **(Probabilistic)Threshold techniques** [eg. studies 42, 172], **Time trade-off (TTO)** [eg. studies 33, 318] and **Visual Analogue Scale (VAS)** [eg. studies 183, 223, 288].

Hence, our systematic review successfully identified five new preference elicitation methods. Specifically, the systematic review successfully identified five preference elicitation methods that were not in Ryan *et al.* [5] and MDIC [8]. These methods identified included **Adaptive conjoint analysis** [eg. studies 1, 88, 124], also known as ACA, which is quite similar to regular conjoint analysis, but with adaptive conjoint, choice tasks are based on the earlier choices made within the survey, in theory allowing the survey to focus attention on those attributes or levels of those attributes that have the most influence on the choices of that individual. **Control preference scales** [eg. study 175] involve participants making a series of paired comparisons to provide their total preference order, by using cards with statements and cartoons. **Outcome prioritization tool** [eg. study 304] is an instrument that allows participants to prioritise outcomes making use of a specific tool according to the “trade-off” principle, implying that they are willing to compromise on the less important outcomes. Prioritization is based on the allocation of a finite amount of points. **Repertory grid method (RGM)** [eg. study 255] is a method for eliciting personal constructs, i.e. what people think about a given topic. To identify preferences overlapping and rating techniques are used. **Starting known efficacy** [eg. study 201] is similar to threshold techniques, but with a specific known starting point.

Figure 4: Method identification overlap between Step 1 (previous related research) and Step 2 (systematic literature review)

Step 3: Expert consultation for validation and confirmation

The experts inside and outside the PREFER project confirmed that the methods included in Step 1 and Step 2 were utilised in the exploration and elicitation of patient preferences. Hence, none were consequently removed at this stage. We also encouraged the experts to identify additional preference exploration and elicitation methods that they found to be lacking from our list. As a result of their expertise, they identified four additional methods. Figure 5 illustrates the method identification overlap between all three of our steps (see Annex III for all their descriptions).

The four new methods identified by experts were exclusively preference elicitation methods (see also Annex III for their descriptions and references). In short, these methods identified included: 1) **Constant sum scaling**, a type of comparative scale where respondents allocate a fixed amount or constant sum among a set of objects according to a criterion; 2) **Q-methodology**, which uses a specially designed response grid to present respondents with a set of statements and asking them to order, usually based on the extent to which they agree with them; 3) **Self-explicated conjoint**, a specific form of conjoint analysis that asks explicitly about the preference for each attribute rather than the preference of several; and 4) **Test trade-off**, a method to evaluate a new biomarker

Figure 5: Method identification overlap between Step 1 (previous related research), Step 2 (systematic literature review) and Step 3 (expert consultation)

(attachment used to indicate an effect) at a specified risk threshold. The test tradeoff corresponding to a risk threshold is the minimum number of tests for a new biomarker that need to be traded for a true positive to yield an increase in the net benefit of risk prediction with the additional biomarker. The test tradeoff can then be considered in light of any detrimental side effects or monetary costs of testing for the biomarker.

By the end of Step 3, we identified 32 exploration and elicitation methods. There are many ways that the methods can be grouped. In our case we grouped the methods according to their methodological relationships (e.g. way of data collection) and the similarities in their techniques (e.g. way of data analysis), as this was the grouping that was most acceptable and crucial among the consulted (inter)national experts. The grouping served to distinguish the particular features of methods that would help a researcher to select one method over another within the context of the research question, the medicinal product the stage in the life cycle.

Figure 6: Preference exploration methods (qualitative) identified in PREFER task 2.4

Figure 6 groups the preference exploration methods according to the number of participants the method utilises in one session. (Semi)structured individual interviews, in-depth interviews and complaints procedures are both preference exploration techniques that conduct interviews with one participant ($n = 1$) in a single setting or session. Delphi method, focus groups, dyadic interviews, public meetings, nominal group technique, and citizen juries are exploration methods that typically direct questions to more than one participant ($n > 1$) in a single setting. Concept mapping is a technique that can employ either individual or group settings during data collection ($n \geq 1$).

Figure 7 groups the preference elicitation methods according to four distinct groups. Firstly, methods that utilise discrete choice (or related) methods are identified. These elicitation methods typically examine the importance of trade-offs between attributes and their alternatives through a series of presented choices. Secondly, threshold related techniques were identified, including methods that aim to reach a point in which the participant is indifferent, or has no preference for one attribute or alternative over another. Thirdly, rating (or related) methods were identified based on their utilisation of comparative rating approaches. Fourthly, ranking (or related) elicitation methods were classified that incorporate ranking exercises.

Figure 7: Preference elicitation methods identified in PREFER task 2.4

Scale related techniques vs. preference elicitation method

A second additional result from the three-step approach was that we identified five scale related techniques that have a role in assessing preferences (see Annex III for the descriptions and references): Verbal Numeric Scale (VNS), Guttman scales, Likert scales, Semantic differential technique (SDT) and Juster's 11 point probability scale. Guttman scales and SDT were identified in step 1, whereas Likert scales was identified in both step 1 and step 2. Both Juster's 11 point probability scale and VNS were identified via the systematic review in step 2 (see studies 311 and 159 respectively). The scale related techniques are relevant as they are sometimes included in lists of preference exploration and elicitation methods to calculate, for example, (attribute) weights. However, these techniques are generally not used to assess preferences themselves, but typically are a component of the instrument used to assess preferences. We therefore decided not to list or count them in our final results in contrast to Ryan *et al.* However, we make an exception for the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). The VAS is used as a rating scale method. Therefore one can argue that VAS is not a preference elicitation method but a scale related technique. However, the VAS is used so frequently to rate health states within the context of medicinal products and medical devices that it has become almost synonymous with the group of scale related techniques itself.

Decision-making framework vs. preference elicitation method

An additional result was our encountered four decision-making framework methods that included weights or preferences (see Annex III for the descriptions and references): Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA); Relative value adjusted need-to-treat (RV-NNT) or relative value adjusted need-to-harm (RV-NNH); Stochastic multi-criteria acceptability analysis (SMAA); and Measuring Attractiveness by a Categorical Based Evaluation Technique (MACBETH). MCDA and RV-NNT / RV-NNH were identified in Step 2 (the systematic review; see ‘studies 44, and 291’ and ‘studies 228 and 303’ respectively), whereas SMAA and MACBETH were suggested by expert opinions in Step 3. These methods have in common that they include weights or preferences as part of a decision-making process, and they are sometimes included in lists of preference exploration and elicitation methods. However, they are processes for decision-making that utilise one or more of the preference exploration and elicitation methods, and they are not preference methods themselves. As a result, we did not list or count them in our final results.

Discussion

We combined a rigorous systematic literature review with evaluation of previous related preference methods reviews and consultation with both experts affiliated and not affiliated with the PREFER project to identify existing patient preference exploration and elicitation methods. Using this three-step approach, we identified 32 preference methods that have been applied to the development of medicinal products and medical devices. These methods were grouped according to their methodological relationships and similarities in their techniques to distinguish the particular features of methods that would help a researcher to select one method over another. It is important to note that some methods might be considered specific variants of other preference methods (e.g. Constant Sum Scaling, Measure of Value, Outcome Prioritization Tool and Starting Known Efficacy) and that there may be no consensus across different scientific fields if the method can indeed be considered a “preference method” (e.g. Control Preferences Scale, Test-Trade-off and Visual Analogue Scale). However, we included these methods in our overview, since the aim of our study was to provide a comprehensive overview of methods and we did not want to exclude methods that were within the scope of our study a priori. In Annex III this point is addressed in more detail.

The results of our systematic review were partly in line with the results found by Ryan et al. [5] and MDIC [8]. Fifty-six percent (13 out of 23) methods reported by Ryan et al. [5] and/or MDIC [8] were identified in our systematic review. The difference can be explained that our search was focused on methods to obtain insights into patient preferences for medicinal products and medical devices, while Ryan *et al.* had a focus on public views on the provision of healthcare. Additionally, MDIC [8] focused exclusively on medical device and excluded preference exploration methods. The presence of 5 additional elicitation methods in our systematic review that were not identified in the two prevalent

preference methods reviews, is mainly caused by the fact that these methods would not have existed yet in the area of healthcare.

The current study has several strengths. First, the three-step approach resulted in an updated overview of methods to elicit patient preferences for medicinal products and medical devices. Confirmation by experts outside of PREFER is important to build a well-funded and accepted basis that helps to develop a systematic approach for considering the use of patient preferences across the medical treatment life cycle; one of the main aims of PREFER [1]. Second, the systematic review was conducted independently by two researchers, which might have a positive effect on reaching a reliable overview of preference exploration and elicitation methods that were applied to medicinal products and medical devices. Third, input was received and taken into account from international experts in the field of health preference research and medical-decision-making, and from different kinds of stakeholders. This helps to reach another important aim of PREFER: to achieve a global, harmonised approach to the use of patient-preference studies by industry, regulatory authorities, HTA bodies, and reimbursement agencies [1].

A potential weakness of our study design is that the systematic review was not optimised to identify all possible/promising methods to elicit patient preferences for medicinal products and medical devices. That is, due to time constraints we had to i) specify the inclusion of medicinal products and medical devices which restricted the focus to those already used for medical applications, and ii) limit the synonyms for a variety of search terms. This might have resulted in preference exploration and elicitation methods of interest not being identified. However, the impact is likely limited given the additional review by international experts with significant experience in health preference elicitation (i.e. Step 3), and reference to the results of two large prior preference methods reviews (i.e. Step 1).

The findings of PREFER task 2.4 are a step towards achieving the main aims of PREFER mentioned above. Our PREFER task 2.4 findings will serve as a direct input for PREFER task 2.6 (i.e. the appraisal of the methods) and PREFER WP3 (i.e. the case studies) to determine which of these 32 methods are most promising to elicit patient preferences, and under what circumstances, throughout the life cycle of medicinal products and medical devices.

Conclusion

In our study, 32 methods utilised to obtain insights into patient preferences were identified. Although all these methods can be used to obtain insights into patient preferences for medicinal products and medical devices, we found that actually 18 out of 32 methods had previously been applied to obtain insights into patient preferences for medicinal products and medical devices. Our findings will serve as the starting point for PREFER task 2.6, in which these methods will be appraised through specific criteria, and PREFER WP3, which will utilise selected methods in case studies. The results of task 2.4 and its subsequent uses in later tasks will help determine which of these methods are most

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promising to obtain insights into patient preferences to support decision-making throughout the lifecycle of medicinal products and medical devices.

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Annexes

Annex I: Search terms and search key overview

Annex II: Overview analysed papers systematic literature review (n=323)

Annex III: Description of patient preference exploration and elicitation methods

Annex I: Search terms and search key overview

Based on the search terms presented in the methods section, the following search query was developed to search for papers in the databases Cochrane Library, Econlit, Embase, PubMed, PsycInfo and Scopus (this query is based on the PubMed database and was translated to other databases when necessary):

```
((patient[tiab] OR patients[tiab] OR client[tiab] OR clients[tiab] OR citizen[tiab] OR citizens[tiab] OR
consumer[tiab] OR consumers[tiab] OR public[tiab] OR general population[tiab]) AND
(Preference[tiab] OR Preferences[tiab] OR Acceptability[tiab] OR utility[tiab] OR utilities[tiab] OR
desirability[tiab]) AND (method[tiab] OR methods[tiab] OR methodology[tiab] OR methodologies[tiab]
OR technique[tiab] OR techniques[tiab] OR measurement[tiab] OR measurements[tiab] OR
instrument[tiab] OR instruments[tiab] OR tool[tiab] OR tools[tiab] OR measure[tiab] OR
measures[tiab] OR approach[tiab] OR approaches[tiab]) AND (elicitation[tiab] OR elicitations[tiab] OR
measuring[tiab] OR determine[tiab] OR determining[tiab] OR explore[tiab]) AND (drug[tiab] OR
drugs[tiab] OR pharmaceutical[tiab] OR pharmaceuticals[tiab] OR medicine[tiab] OR medicines[tiab]
OR medication[tiab] OR medications[tiab] OR medicament[tiab] OR medicaments[tiab] OR "medical
device"[tiab] OR "medical devices"[tiab] OR "medical instrument"[tiab] OR "medical
instruments"[tiab])) AND ("loattrfull text"[sb] AND ("1980/01/01"[PDAT] : "2016/12/31"[PDAT]) AND
"humans"[MeSH Terms] AND English[lang])
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Annex II: Overview of analysed papers in the systematic literature review (n=323)

Study	Authors	Title	Journal	Year
1	Abraham NS, Naik AD, Street RL, et al	Complex antithrombotic therapy: Determinants of patient preference and impact on medication adherence	Patient Preference and Adherence	2015
2	Ackerman IN, Jordan JE, Van Doornum S, et al	Understanding the information needs of women with rheumatoid arthritis concerning pregnancy, post-natal care and early parenting: A mixed-methods study	BMC Musculoskelet Disord	2015
3	Ahmad Y, Nijjer S, Cook CM, et al	A new method of applying randomised control study data to the individual patient: A novel quantitative patient-centred approach to interpreting composite end points	Int J Cardiol	2015
4	Aikens JE, Nease DE, Jr., Nau DP, et al	"Adherence to maintenance-phase antidepressant medication as a function of patient beliefs about medication": Correction	Annals of Family Medicine	2005
5	Aikens JE, Nease DE, Jr., Nau DP, et al	Adherence to maintenance-phase antidepressant medication as a function of patient beliefs about medication	Ann Fam Med	2005
6	Alam M, Arifeen S	A qualitative research to understand public perception of personalised cancer medicine (PCM) and its application in treatment of advanced lung cancer	Asia-Pacific Journal of Clinical Oncology	2015
7	Aleem IS, Jalal H, Aleem IS, et al	Clinical decision analysis: Incorporating the evidence with patient preferences	Patient Preference and Adherence	2009
8	Al-Omari B, Frisher M, Croft P, et al	Using adaptive choice based conjoint (ACBC) analysis to study patients' preferences regarding pharmaceutical treatment for osteoarthritis (OA)	Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases	2013

9	Alonso-Coello P, Montori VM, Sola I, et al	Values and preferences in oral anticoagulation in patients with atrial fibrillation, physicians' and patients' perspectives: protocol for a two-phase study	BMC Health Serv Res	2008
10	Altice FL, Mostashari F, Friedland GH	Trust and the acceptance of and adherence to antiretroviral therapy	J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr	2001
11	Ambrose PG, Hammel JP, Bhavnani SM, et al	Frequentist and Bayesian pharmacometric-based approaches to facilitate critically needed new antibiotic development: overcoming lies, damn lies, and statistics	Antimicrob Agents Chemother	2012
12	Anderson P	Patient preference for and satisfaction with inhaler devices	European Respiratory Review	2005
13	Andrade JG, Krahn AD, Skanes AC, et al	Values and Preferences of Physicians and Patients With Nonvalvular Atrial Fibrillation Who Receive Oral Anticoagulation Therapy for Stroke Prevention	Canadian Journal of Cardiology	2016
14	Anink J, Otten MH, Gorter SL, et al	Treatment choices of paediatric rheumatologists for juvenile idiopathic arthritis: etanercept or adalimumab?	Rheumatology (Oxford)	2013
15	Anquinet L, Raus K, Sterckx S, et al	Comparing continuous sedation until death and euthanasia: Professional caregivers' attitudes and experiences. A focus group study in flanders, belgium	Palliative Medicine	2012
16	Arendts G, Howard K, Rose JM	Allocation decisions and patient preferences in emergency medicine	Emerg Med J	2011
17	Arkell P, Ryan S, Brownfield A, et al	Patient experiences, attitudes and expectations towards receiving information about anti-TNF: A qualitative study	Rheumatology (United Kingdom)	2012
18	Arkinson J, Holbrook A, Wiercioch W	Public perceptions of physician-pharmaceutical industry interactions: A systematic review	Healthcare Policy	2010
19	Ashcroft DM, Seston E, Griffiths CE	Trade-offs between the benefits and risks of drug treatment for psoriasis: a discrete choice experiment with U.K. Dermatologists	Br J Dermatol	2006

20	Ashton H, Nodiyal A, Green D, et al	Acupuncture or counselling: Outcomes and predictors of treatment choice in a non-statutory addiction service	Journal of Substance Use	2009
21	Astin F, Closs SJ, McLenachan J, et al	The information needs of patients treated with primary angioplasty for heart attack: an exploratory study	Patient Educ Couns	2008
22	Athar MW, Mativo C, Landis R, et al	Communication of laboratory data and diagnostic test results to hospitalized patients: A study of preferences and recall	Patient Preference and Adherence	2016
23	Attipoe L, Ciurtin C	Does health satisfaction and perception of treatment efficacy in patients with inflammatory arthritis correlate with disability and global health state?	Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases	2015
24	Bader P, McDonald P, Selby P	An algorithm for tailoring pharmacotherapy for smoking cessation: results from a Delphi panel of international experts	Tob Control	2009
25	Baji P, Gulácsi L, Golovics PA, et al	Perceived Risks Contra Benefits of Using Biosimilar Drugs in Ulcerative Colitis: Discrete Choice Experiment among Gastroenterologists	Value in Health Regional Issues	2016
26	Baji P, Gulacsi L, Lovasz BD, et al	Treatment preferences of originator versus biosimilar drugs in Crohn's disease: discrete choice experiment among gastroenterologists	Scand J Gastroenterol	2016
27	Bakirtas A, Kutlu A, Baccioglu A, et al	Physicians' preference for controller medication in mild persistent asthma	European Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology	2016
28	Bardet JD, Vo TH, Bosson JL, et al	Patients', physicians' and pharmacists' viewpoints on the implementation of medication reviews in the French primary care	International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy	2015
29	Barron AC, Lee TL, Taylor J, et al	Feasibility and construct validity of the parent willingness-to-pay technique for children with juvenile idiopathic arthritis	Arthritis Rheum	2004
30	Belcher VN, Fried TR, Agostini JV, et al	Views of older adults on patient participation in medication-related decision	J Gen Intern Med	2006

		making		
31	Bell CM, Chapman RH, Stone PW, et al	An off-the-shelf help list: a comprehensive catalog of preference scores from published cost-utility analyses	Med Decis Making	2001
32	Benson J, Britten N	What effects do patients feel from their antihypertensive tablets and how do they react to them? Qualitative analysis of interviews with patients	Fam Pract	2006
33	Beukelman T, Guevara JP, Albert DA	Optimal treatment of knee monarthritis in juvenile idiopathic arthritis: a decision analysis	Arthritis Rheum	2008
34	Bewtra M, Johnson FR	Assessing patient preferences for treatment options and process of care in inflammatory bowel disease: a critical review of quantitative data	Patient	2013
35	Beyhun NE, Kosan Z, Aras A, et al	Willingness to receive the influenza A(H1N1) vaccine and its determinants among university students during the 2009 outbreak in Turkey	Eurasian Journal of Medicine	2014
36	Bhargava JS, Patel B, Foss AJ, et al	Views of glaucoma patients on aspects of their treatment: an exploration of patient preference by conjoint analysis	Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci	2006
37	Bime C, Wei C, Nguyen J, et al	Asthma symptom utility index: Reliability, validity, responsiveness and the minimally important clinical difference in adult asthma patients	American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine	2012
38	Bislew HD, Sorensen TD	Use of focus groups as a tool to enhance a pharmaceutical care practice	Journal of the American Pharmacists Association : JAPhA	2003
39	Blank T, Graves K, Sepucha K, et al	Understanding treatment decision making: Contexts, commonalities, complexities, and challenges	Annals of Behavioral Medicine	2006

40	Bonistalli L, Bardelli F, Constantini M, et al	Adjuvant chemotherapy in patients with resectable stage III colon cancer: Lifetime cost-effectiveness and cost-utility analysis	Cancer Journal	1998
41	Borgsteede SD, Karapinar-Carkit F, Hoffmann E, et al	Information needs about medication according to patients discharged from a general hospital	Patient Educ Couns	2011
42	Brett Hauber A, Fairchild AO, Reed Johnson F	Quantifying Benefit-Risk Preferences for Medical Interventions: An Overview of a Growing Empirical Literature	Applied Health Economics and Health Policy	2013
43	Brockbank S, Miller N, Owen S, et al	Pretreatment information on dysphagia: Exploring the views of head and neck cancer patients	Journal of Pain and Symptom Management	2015
44	Broekhuizen H, Ijzerman MJ, Hauber AB, et al	Weighing Clinical Evidence Using Patient Preferences: An Application of Probabilistic Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis	PharmacoEconomics	2016
45	Bryson SP	Patient-centred, administration friendly medicines for children - an evaluation of children's preferences and how they impact medication adherence	Int J Pharm	2014
46	Buttery A, Lowton K, Glaser K, et al	Older heart failure patients' preferences for cardiac rehabilitation service models	European Heart Journal	2011
47	Caffey M, Maria S, Ireland M, et al	Antiemetic management preferences for Australasian paramedic providers	Australasian Journal of Paramedicine	2016
48	Cai QF, Wan F, Dong XY, et al	Fertility clinicians and infertile patients in China have different preferences in fertility care	Hum Reprod	2014
49	Carlesso LC, MacDermid JC, Gross AR, et al	Treatment preferences amongst physical therapists and chiropractors for the management of neck pain: Results of an international survey	Chiropractic and Manual Therapies	2014
50	Casarett D, Van Ness PH, O'Leary JR, et al	Are patient preferences for life-sustaining treatment really a barrier to hospice enrollment for older adults with serious illness?	J Am Geriatr Soc	2006

51	Castro JG, Jones DL, Weiss SM	STD patients' preferences for HIV prevention strategies	HIV/AIDS - Research and Palliative Care	2014
52	Celio J, Maeder S, Halabi G, et al	Chronic dialysis, medication adherence and beliefs about medicines: A comparison between patients born in Switzerland and migrant patients (diana study)	International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy	2016
53	Charles C, Gafni A	The vexing problem of defining the meaning, role and measurement of values in treatment decision-making	J Comp Eff Res	2014
54	Chater AM, Parham R, Riley S, et al	Profiling patient attitudes to phosphate binding medication: a route to personalising treatment and adherence support	Psychol Health	2014
55	Chatterjee A, DePriest K, Blair R, et al	Results of a survey of blood pressure monitoring by intensivists in critically ill patients: a preliminary study	Crit Care Med	2010
56	Chaudhry IB, Rahman R, Minhas HM, et al	Which antidepressant would psychiatrists and nurses from a developing country choose for themselves?	Int J Psychiatry Clin Pract	2011
57	Chen LC, Cheng LJ, Zhang Y, et al	Acupuncture or low frequency infrared treatment for low back pain in Chinese patients: a discrete choice experiment	PLoS One	2015
58	Chilton F, Collett RA	Treatment choices, preferences and decision-making by patients with rheumatoid arthritis	Musculoskeletal Care	2008
59	Chilvers C, Dewey M, Fielding K, et al	Antidepressant drugs and generic counselling for treatment of major depression in primary care: randomised trial with patient preference arms	Bmj	2001
60	Chuma J, Okungu V, Molyneux C	Barriers to prompt and effective malaria treatment among the poorest population in Kenya	Malaria Journal	2010
61	Chung IW, Kim YS, Lee NY, et al	Preference for long-acting injectable antipsychotics of community-dwelling patients with schizophrenia and their caregivers in Korea	International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology	2014

62	Chung VCH, Ma PHX, Lau CH, et al	Developing policy for integrating biomedicine and traditional Chinese medical practice using focus groups and the Delphi technique	Evidence-based Complementary and Alternative Medicine	2012
63	Cimminiello C, Anderson FA, Jr	Physician and patient perceptions of the route of administration of venous thromboembolism prophylaxis: results from an international survey	Thromb Res	2012
64	Clark DO, Kroenke K, Callahan CM, et al	Validity and utility of patient-reported health measures on hospital admission	J Clin Epidemiol	1999
65	Clatworthy J, Bowskill R, Rank T, et al	Adherence to medication in bipolar disorder: a qualitative study exploring the role of patients' beliefs about the condition and its treatment	Bipolar Disord	2007
66	Constantinescu F, Goucher S, Weinstein A, et al	Understanding why rheumatoid arthritis patient treatment preferences differ by race	Arthritis Rheum	2009
67	D'Abramo F, Schildmann J, Vollmann J	Research participants' perceptions and views on consent for biobank research: a review of empirical data and ethical analysis	BMC Med Ethics	2015
68	Daftary A, Padayatchi N, O'Donnell M	Preferential adherence to antiretroviral therapy over tuberculosis treatment: a qualitative study of drug-resistant TB/HIV co-infected patients in South Africa	Glob Public Health	2014
69	Dana Lamond NW, Skedgel C, Rayson D, et al	Adjuvant denosumab for breast cancer: What efficacy in the D-CARE trial will translate into cost effectiveness?	Journal of Clinical Oncology	2014
70	Dhanani MT, Wells AE, Montgomery TL, et al	Patient attitudes regarding the use of power morcellation during laparoscopic hysterectomy	Gynecologic Oncology	2015
71	Dickinson R, Hamrosi K, Knapp P, et al	Written medicines information in the UK and Australia: Exploring patient opinions and preferences on tailoring medicine leaflets	International Journal of Pharmacy Practice	2011

72	Dickinson R, Hamrosi K, Knapp P, et al	Suits you? A qualitative study exploring preferences regarding the tailoring of consumer medicines information	Int J Pharm Pract	2013
73	Dong D, Ozdemir S, Mong Bee Y, et al	Measuring High-Risk Patients' Preferences for Pharmacogenetic Testing to Reduce Severe Adverse Drug Reaction: A Discrete Choice Experiment	Value in Health	2016
74	Doos L, Bradley E, Rushton CA, et al	Heart failure and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease multimorbidity at hospital discharge transition: a study of patient and carer experience	Health Expect	2015
75	Dowdy D, Bishai D, Chen AH	Setting clinical priorities: A framework for incorporating individual patient preferences	Patient Education and Counseling	2013
76	Dowse R	Reflecting on patient-centred care in pharmacy through an illness narrative	Int J Clin Pharm	2015
77	Dragojlovic N, Rizzardo S, Bansback N, et al	Challenges in measuring the societal value of orphan drugs: insights from a canadian stated preference survey	Patient	2015
78	Dranitsaris G, Leung P	Using decision modeling to determine pricing of new pharmaceuticals: The case of neurokinin-1 receptor antagonist antiemetics for cancer chemotherapy	International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care	2004
79	Duarte JW, Bolge SC, Sen SS	An evaluation of patients' preferences for osteoporosis medications and their attributes: the PREFER-International study	Clin Ther	2007
80	Dwight-Johnson M, Lagomasino IT, Aisenberg E, et al	Using conjoint analysis to assess depression treatment preferences among low-income Latinos	Psychiatr Serv	2004
81	Emoto N, Okajima F, Sugihara H, et al	Behavioral economics survey of patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes	Patient Preference and Adherence	2015
82	Ende J, Kazis L, Ash A, et al	Measuring patients' desire for autonomy - Decision making and information-seeking preferences among medical patients	Journal of General Internal Medicine	1989

83	Fargher E, Hughes D, Ring A, et al	Using discrete choice experiments to define patient preferences for outcomes in trials	Trials	2013
84	Feldman SR, Housman TS	Patients' vehicle preference for corticosteroid treatments of scalp psoriasis	Am J Clin Dermatol	2003
85	Finckh A, Escher M, Liang MH, et al	Factors involved in the decision to take medications to prevent rheumatoid arthritis in first degree relatives of patients with rheumatoid arthritis: A discrete choice experiment	Arthritis and Rheumatism	2011
86	Fischer GS, Tulsy JA, Rose MR, et al	Patient knowledge and physician predictions of treatment preferences after discussion of advance directives	J Gen Intern Med	1998
87	Fraenkel L, Bogardus ST, Jr. , Concato J, et al	Treatment options in knee osteoarthritis: the patient's perspective	Arch Intern Med	2004
88	Fraenkel L, Gulanski B, Wittink D	Patient treatment preferences for osteoporosis	Arthritis Rheum	2006
89	Fraenkel L, Gulanski B, Wittink D	Patient willingness to take teriparatide	Patient Educ Couns	2007
90	Fraenkel L, Gulanski B, Wittink DR	Preference for hip protectors among older adults at high risk for osteoporotic fractures	J Rheumatol	2006
91	Fukuda M, Suetsugu T, Ebi N, et al	Which do patients with nsclc harboring EGFR mutation prefer EGFR-TKI or chemotherapy? A vignettes study (logik0903)	Annals of Oncology	2013
92	Fullerton L, Cesta A, Hofstetter C, et al	Patient priorities in ra research-an exploration of patient perspectives from those enrolled in the Ontario best practices research initiative (OBRI) clinical registry	Journal of Rheumatology	2015
93	Fyffe HE, Kay EJ	Assessment of dental health state utilities	Community Dent Oral Epidemiol	1992
94	Gale NK, Greenfield S, Gill P, et al	Patient and general practitioner attitudes to taking medication to prevent cardiovascular disease after receiving detailed information on risks and benefits of treatment: a qualitative study	BMC Fam Pract	2011

95	Ganther JM, Wiederholt JB, Kreling DH	Measuring patients' medical care preferences: care seeking versus self-treating	Med Decis Making	2001
96	Garrison LP, Jr., Towse A, Bresnahan BW	Assessing a structured, quantitative health outcomes approach to drug risk-benefit analysis	Health Aff (Millwood)	2007
97	Gauthier B, Singh SR, Virani A, et al	Perspectives and experiences of health care professionals and patients regarding treatments for type 2 diabetes	Canadian Pharmacists Journal	2014
98	Gauthier C, Lindwall E, Davis W, et al	Spanning generations-appointment reminder preferences among patients with rheumatic diseases	J Clin Rheumatol	2012
99	Gazzard B, Leen C, Morton J, et al	Evaluation of patient satisfaction with antiretroviral therapy using a discrete choice experiment	HIV Medicine	2015
100	Gelhorn HL, Bacci ED, Poon JL, et al	Evaluating preferences for profiles of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists among injection-naïve type 2 diabetes patients in Japan	Patient Preference and Adherence	2016
101	Gelhorn HL, Poon JL, Davies EW, et al	Evaluating preferences for profiles of GLP-1 receptor agonists among injection-naïve type 2 diabetes patients in the UK	Patient Preference and Adherence	2015
102	Gerard K, Salisbury C, Street D, et al	Is fast access to general practice all that should matter? A discrete choice experiment of patients' preferences	Journal of Health Services Research and Policy	2008
103	Gestuvo MK	Health maintenance in older adults: Combining evidence and individual preferences	Mount Sinai Journal of Medicine	2012
104	Giebel GD, Groeben N	Social desirability in the measuring of patient satisfaction after treatment of coloproctologic disorders: on shortcomings of general bipolar satisfaction scales for quality management	Langenbecks Arch Surg	2008
105	Goertzel BN, Pennachin C, de Souza Coelho L, et al	Allostatic load is associated with symptoms in chronic fatigue syndrome patients	Pharmacogenomics	2006

106	Gold DT, Safi W, Trinh H	Patient preference and adherence: Comparative US studies between two bisphosphonates, weekly risedronate and monthly ibandronate	Current Medical Research and Opinion	2006
107	Gopal C, Ranga A, Joseph K, et al	Development and validation of algorithms for heart failure patient care: A Delphi study	International Journal of Pharmacy Practice	2014
108	Gould O, Buckley P, Doucette D	What patients want: Preferences regarding hospital pharmacy services	Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy	2013
109	Grindrod KA, Marra CA, Colley L, et al	Pharmacists' preferences for providing patient-centered services: a discrete choice experiment to guide health policy	Ann Pharmacother	2010
110	Grubbs V, Bibbins-Domingo K, Fernandez A, et al	Acute myocardial infarction length of stay and hospital mortality are not associated with language preference	Journal of General Internal Medicine	2008
111	Guevara BEK, Gonzales N, Visitacion L	Patient preference on psoriasis treatment in a Philippine Tertiary Hospital: A conjoint analysis	Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology	2016
112	Guirguis LM, Nusair MB	Standardized patients' preferences for pharmacist interactive communication style: A mixed method approach	Journal of the American Pharmacists Association	2016
113	Gupta VK, Bahia JS, Maheshwari A, et al	To study the attitudes, beliefs and perceptions regarding the use of inhalers among patients of obstructive pulmonary diseases and in the general population in Punjab	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research	2011
114	Hall J, Viney R, Haas M, et al	Using stated preference discrete choice modeling to evaluate health care programs	Journal of Business Research	2004
115	Hames H, Seabrook JA, Matsui D, et al	A palatability study of a flavored dexamethasone preparation versus prednisolone liquid in children	Journal canadien de pharmacologie clinique [Canadian journal of clinical pharmacology]	2008
116	Hamrosi K, Dickinson R, Knapp P, et al	It's for your benefit: exploring patients' opinions about the inclusion of textual and numerical benefit information	Int J Pharm Pract	2013

		in medicine leaflets		
117	Hancock-Howard RL, Ungar WJ, Marshall D, et al	Public preferences for counseling regarding antidepressant use during pregnancy: a discrete choice experiment	Birth Defects Res A Clin Mol Teratol	2012
118	Hanson KA, Agashivala N, Wyrwich KW, et al	Treatment selection and experience in multiple sclerosis: Survey of neurologists	Patient Preference and Adherence	2014
119	Harrison M, Marra C, Shojania K, et al	Societal preferences for rheumatoid arthritis treatments: evidence from a discrete choice experiment	Rheumatology (Oxford)	2015
120	Hart RI, McDonagh JE, Thompson B, et al	Being as Normal as Possible: How Young People Ages 16–25 Years Evaluate the Risks and Benefits of Treatment for Inflammatory Arthritis	Arthritis Care and Research	2016
121	Hayes RP, Bowman L, Monahan PO, et al	Understanding diabetes medications from the perspective of patients with type 2 diabetes: prerequisite to medication concordance	Diabetes Educ	2006
122	Hazlewood G, Marshall D, Tomlinson G, et al	Treatment preferences of patients with early rheumatoid arthritis: A discrete-choice experiment	Journal of Rheumatology	2015
123	Heinze G, Cortés JF	Treatment preference and attitude toward pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy in Latin America. ULAD Task Force	Salud Mental	2005
124	Hess LM, Litwiller A, Byron J, et al	Preference elicitation tool for abnormal uterine bleeding treatment: a randomized controlled trial	Patient	2015
125	Hill-Smith I, Mathie E, Little P	Involving patients in decisions about preventive medication: A focus group study	Primary Care Cardiovascular Journal	2010
126	Hincapie A, Penm J, Burns C	A conjoint analysis of disease-modifying drugs used in the treatment of autoimmune conditions	Journal of the American Pharmacists Association	2016

127	Hissink MPCE, Brederije I, Brinkman DMC, et al	Parental preferences for treatment: Preliminary report from a randomised comparison of treatment strategies in (early) juvenile idiopathic arthritis (BeSt for Kids trial)	Pediatric Rheumatology	2011
128	Hlubocky FJ, Ratain MJ, Wen M, et al	Complementary and alternative medicine among advanced cancer patients enrolled on phase I trials: a study of prognosis, quality of life, and preferences for decision making	J Clin Oncol	2007
129	Hobson RJ, Scott J, Sutton J	Pharmacists and nurses as independent prescribers: exploring the patient's perspective	Fam Pract	2010
130	Hoffmann C, Rosenberger A, Troeger W, et al	Validation of questionnaires from several medical fields regarding the constitution of patients	Forschende Komplementarmedizin und Klassische Naturheilkunde	2002
131	Holbrook K	A triangulation study of the clinician and patient experiences of the use of the immunosuppressant drugs azathioprine and 6-mercaptopurine for the management of inflammatory bowel disease	J Clin Nurs	2007
132	Holden WL	Benefit-risk analysis : a brief review and proposed quantitative approaches	Drug Saf	2003
133	Hollin IL, Peay HL, Bridges JF	Caregiver preferences for emerging duchenne muscular dystrophy treatments: a comparison of best-worst scaling and conjoint analysis	Patient	2015
134	Holmes EAF, Morrison VL, Hughes DA	What influences persistence with medicines? A multinational discrete choice experiment of 2549 patients	British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology	2016
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310	White JH, Towers SE, Turner A, et al	Electronic screening and decision support for poststroke depression: An exploration of doctors' and patients' perceptions of acceptability	Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation	2013
311	Whitty JA, Rundle-Thiele SR, Scuffham PA	Insights from triangulation of two purchase choice elicitation methods to predict social decision making in healthcare	Appl Health Econ Health Policy	2012
312	Wilson L, Loucks A, Bui C, et al	Patient centered decision making: use of conjoint analysis to determine risk-benefit trade-offs for preference sensitive treatment choices	J Neurol Sci	2014

313	Wittink MN, Cary M, TenHave T, et al	Towards patient-centered care for depression: Conjoint methods to tailor treatment based on preferences	Patient	2010
314	Wolfe F, Zhao S, Lane N	Preference for nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs over acetaminophen by rheumatic disease patients: a survey of 1,799 patients with osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and fibromyalgia	Arthritis Rheum	2000
315	Wong A, Kraus PS, Lau BD, et al	Patient preferences regarding pharmacologic venous thromboembolism prophylaxis	J Hosp Med	2015
316	Woolf SH, Krist AH, Johnson RE, et al	Unwanted control: how patients in the primary care setting decide about screening for prostate cancer	Patient Educ Couns	2005
317	Wu F, Peng CY, Jiang H, et al	Methadone maintenance treatment in China: perceived challenges from the perspectives of service providers and patients	J Public Health (Oxf)	2013
318	Wu JM, Fulton RG, Amundsen CL, et al	Patient preferences for different severities of and treatments for overactive bladder	Female Pelvic Medicine and Reconstructive Surgery	2011
319	Yarris LM, Moreno R, Schmidt TA, et al	Reasons why patients choose an ambulance and willingness to consider alternatives	Academic Emergency Medicine	2006
320	Zafar AM, Harris TJ, Murphy TP, et al	Patients' perspective about risks and benefits of treatment for peripheral arterial disease	J Vasc Interv Radiol	2011
321	Zhang G, Parikh PB, Zabihi S, et al	Rating the preferences for potential harms of treatments for cardiovascular disease: a survey of community-dwelling adults	Med Decis Making	2013
322	Zipursky RB, Cunningham CE, Bieling P, et al	Evaluating patient preferences for early intervention services using discrete choice conjoint analysis	Schizophrenia Research	2012
323	Zuchowski JL, Hamilton AB, Pyne JM, et al	Qualitative analysis of patient-centered decision attributes associated with initiating hepatitis C treatment	BMC Gastroenterol	2015

Annex III: Description of patient preference exploration and elicitation methods

Preference exploration methods

1. Citizens' juries

Citizens' juries consist of a group of people, representing the lay population, which discuss issues on the basis of evidence provided by experts. Jurors are briefed about the topic in question, are given written information and listen to evidence from witnesses. Citizens' juries usually occur over a period of 4 days and consist of a small group of up to 20 members. Participants are usually selected using random and stratified sampling to be as representative of their community as possible. Juries should include one or two trained moderators (Mitton, Smith, Peacock, Evoy, & Abelson, 2009; Street, Duszynski, Krawczyk, & Braunack-Mayer, 2014).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from a lay person sample about the topics addressed by the expert evidence, including potentially patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

2. Complaints procedures

With complaints procedures a system is set in place where stakeholders can register their complaints. These complaints will be investigated by experts. Different authorities have been cited as using such an approach (Bourne et al., 2015; Wensing & Grol, 1998). Noteworthy, this approach might yield a highly biased sample, which would hamper the generalizability of the results.

Main outcome: Qualitative data from a sample of stakeholders about those topics inducing complaints, including potentially patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

3. Concept mapping

Concept mapping has been suggested as an alternative method to using focus groups. It is very similar to focus groups, but it ensures that all members have an equal opportunity to express opinion by eliminating the problems that group dynamics can cause. Additionally, it uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods (Burke et al., 2005; Trochim & Kane, 2005).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from respondents about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

4. Delphi method

The Delphi method is a structured communication technique which relies on a panel of experts. The experts answer questionnaires anonymously in two or more rounds, of which at least the final round is analyzed quantitatively. After each round, a facilitator provides an anonymous summary of the experts' responses from the previous round as well as the reasons they provided for their judgments.

Experts are encouraged to revise their earlier answers in light of the replies of other members of their panel. Finally, the process is stopped after a predefined stop criterion (e.g. number of rounds, achievement of consensus, stability of results). The mean or median scores of the final round(s) determine the results (Boulkedid, Abdoul, Loustau, Sibony, & Alberti, 2011; Julian de, 2003).

Main outcome: Qualitative or quantitative data from respondents about the topics addressed in the questionnaires, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. The quantitative assessments will not include any statistical measures other than respondent standard deviation and number of rounds until the stop criterion is met.

5. Dyadic interview

In dyadic interviews, two participants interact in response to open-ended research questions. This technique is similar to focus groups, see below, but in a smaller setting (Eisikovits & Koren, 2010; Morgan, Ataie, Carder, & Hoffman, 2013).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from two participants about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

6. Focus group

A focus group is a group of interacting individuals with characteristics in common that relate to the topic of the focus group. A moderator uses the group and its interaction to obtain information about a specific or focused issue. Focus groups typically consist of 7-10 people who are unfamiliar with each other. The moderator creates a permissive and nurturing environment that encourages different perceptions and points of view, without pressuring participants to vote, plan or reach consensus. Focus group discussions are typically conducted several times with similar types of participants to identify trends and patterns in perceptions. Systematic analysis of the discussions provide clues and insights as to how a product, service, or opportunity is perceived by the group (Basch, 1987; Schulze & Angermeyer, 2003).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from respondents about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

7. Nominal group technique

A consensus method similar to the Delphi technique. This method was developed to avoid the problems of group interaction (e.g., peer pressure, tension) and provides a quantitative measure of qualitative data. In one meeting ideas can be generated and problems solved. The meetings facilitated by a third party, and major issues affecting the group are identified and ranked. This method is considered appropriate for prioritizing interventions and effective at obtaining consensus (add reference). There are a number of steps in this highly structured process: Participants in the group write down their own ideas, the ideas of each participant are then listed one by one, and these

suggestions are discussed and grouped into clusters. Each participant then ranks the ideas in order of importance, the ranking is discussed and ideas are re-ranked as a group. Feedback of the final results is provided (Allen, Dyas, & Jones, 2004; Gallagher, Hares, Spencer, Bradshaw, & Webb, 1993).

Main outcome: Qualitative or quantitative data from respondents about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

8. Public meetings

Public meetings are a common means to gain public opinion relating to multiple issues. Plans and proposals are sent to stakeholders in advance for comment, and meetings are arranged to obtain a feel for attitudes towards these. Many authorities use public meetings as a means to provide information to communities and to gauge public opinion on health issues (Ham, 1997; McComas, 2001).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from the public about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

9. (Semi)structured-individual interview

A (semi)structured-individual interview is a specific interview technique. A semi-structured interview is a technique where the interviewer follows an open interview technique, allowing new ideas to be brought up during the interview as a result of what the interviewee says. The interviewer in a (semi)structured-interview has a framework of themes to be explored, but the interviewer may stray from the predefined questions (Louise Barriball & While, 1994; Whiting, 2008). In a structured interview an interviewer follows a list of questions that cannot be deviated from.

Main outcome: Qualitative data from the respondent about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

10. In-depth-individual interview

In depth individual interviews the interviewer follows a set of questions and based on the answers of the interviewee the interviewer asks follow-up questions. These questions have generally not been prepared in advance. The general aim of this technique is to get a deeper understanding of a specific topic or theme (Harris et al., 2000; Williams, 1988).

Main outcome: Qualitative data from the respondent about the topics addressed, which may include patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

Preference elicitation methods

11. Adaptive Conjoint Analysis

Adaptive Conjoint Analysis (ACA) is a specific form of conjoint analysis. Generally, in conjoint analysis, individuals are asked to choose amongst complete profiles for a product or service, with the particular sets of profiles shown determined in advance by an experimental design. The profiles include all attributes (benefits, harms, costs, etc.) that define the product or service in the survey. In adaptive conjoint analysis, partial or complete profiles may be used, and the particular partial or complete profiles shown are based on the earlier choices made within the survey, in theory allowing the survey to focus attention on those attributes or levels of those attributes that have the most influence on the choices of that individual, eventually leading to the calculation of preferences to reflect the relative desirability or acceptability (Beusterien, Dziekan, Flood, Harding, & Jordan, 2005; Fraenkel, Bodardus, & Wittink, 2001).

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. utilities reflecting preference for each level of each attribute) about patient preferences regarding medical products. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between attributes (or its levels) and/or alternatives. Can provide attribute relative importance, willingness to pay, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, uncertainty tolerance, or preference heterogeneity and potential uptake rates.

12. Allocation of points

Allocation of points is a technique used to measure preferences related to alternative options or attributes by allocating points to them. This technique either assumes that individuals know the weights they assign and can state them, or it is used to determine these weights. In one approach, respondents are asked to rate how affected they are by their condition on a scale from 0 to 100, where 0 represents the worst possible situation and 100 the best. Respondents are then given a specified number of points and asked to spend them on improving a list of attributes. The points they assign represent the relative importance of each attribute (Haywood, Garratt, Dziedzic, & Dawes, 2003; Schwappach & Strasmann, 2006). In an alternative approach, respondents are given 100 points to allocate amongst a given level of several attributes (benefit, harms, etc.) according to how important that attribute is when making a treatment decision.

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. Can provide attribute relative importance, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, and potentially preference heterogeneity. Generally is unable to provide uncertainty tolerance or how relative importance differs over a wide range of attribute values.

13. Analytic Hierarchy Process

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is used to assess the relative importance (weights) of different

attributes in the provision of a good or service, and following on from this, to derive scores for given alternative goods and services. AHP requires that changes in the levels of each attribute are compared to derive weights that indicate the relative importance of changes in attribute levels to achieving a decision goal. This is accomplished through a series of pairwise comparisons between every pair of attributes. The responder indicates which attribute is preferred, is more likely, or is more important as well as the strength of their preference. Software interrogates a patient when choices are contradictory. These comparisons then are used to compute a weight for each attribute to reflect the relative desirability or acceptability among attributes (Liberatore & Nydick, 2008; Vaidya & Kumar, 2006, MDIC, 2015).

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. scores) about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. Generally used to compute weights for attributes.

14. Best-Worst Scaling (Types 1, 2, 3)

Best-Worst scaling consists of three types: Type 1:object case, Type 2:single-profile case, and Type 3:multiple-profile case. In all cases, individuals are presented with a set of alternatives and asked to identify the best or most important alternative and the worst or least important alternative. In the object case, attributes are combined into sets, or possibly complete profiles of a treatment. Each set does not necessarily (and often does not) include all attributes. For each of a series of sets, individuals are asked to indicate which of the attributes in the set is best or most desirable and which is worst or least desirable. In the single-profile case, each attribute takes on different levels. The attribute levels are combined into profiles. Individuals are presented with a series of profiles and asked to indicate which attribute level in the profile is best or most desirable and which attribute level in the profile is worst or least desirable. In the multiple-profile case, attribute levels are combined into profiles, and the profiles are combined into sets of three or more. The multiple-profile case is very similar to DCEs, individuals are asked to indicate which profile is best or most desirable and which profile is worst or least desirable. In all three types of best-worst scaling, the pattern of responses is analysed to estimate the relative importance of each attribute or attribute level (Flynn, 2010; Flynn, Louviere, Peters, & Coast, 2007; MDIC 2015).

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. utilities reflecting preference for each level of each attribute) about patient preferences regarding medical products. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between attributes (or its levels) and/or alternatives. Can provide attribute relative importance, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, uncertainty tolerance, preference heterogeneity and potential uptake rates.

15. Constant sum scaling

Constant sum scaling consists of a comparative scale where respondents are asked to allocate a fixed amount (or constant sum) of points, dollars, or anything among a set of objects according to a

criterion (Mai & Hoffmann, 2012; Skedgel, Wailoo, & Akehurst, 2015). This method is quite similar to allocation of points. The main difference is that with allocation of points, points are used for allocation, whereas with constant sum scaling other units might be used for allocation tasks.

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. rating) about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

16. Contingent valuation

Contingent valuation is a choice-based approach to determine the willingness to pay (WTP), where individuals are presented with a choice between not having the commodity valued, and having the commodity but forgoing a certain amount of money. The money being that they are willing to forgo to have the commodity is their WTP for that commodity, which provides information about the relative desirability or acceptability of that commodity. WTP can be calculated in a direct or indirect way (via DCE for example) (Bärnighausen, Liu, Zhang, & Sauerborn, 2007; Cunningham & Hunt, 2000).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about the amount of money respondents are willing to forgo regarding different choices. These amounts can be used to obtain insight in the preferences of patients regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

17. Control Preferences Scale

The control preferences scale (CPS) is defined as "the degree of control an individual wants to assume when decisions are being made about medical treatment." The CPS consists of five cards that each portray a different role in treatment decision-making using a statement and a cartoon. These roles range from the individual making the treatment decision, through the individual making the decision jointly with the physician, to the physician making the decision. The CPS involves subjects in making a series of paired comparisons to provide their total preference order over the five cards. The preference orders are analyzed using unfolding theory to determine the distribution of preferences in different populations and the effect of covariates on consumer preferences (Degner, Sloan, & Venkatesh, 1997; McPherson, Higginson, & Hearn, 2001, Henrikson, Davison & Berry, 2011).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about the preference distribution of patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices and the factors influencing these preferences.

18. Discrete Choice Experiment

In discrete-choice experiments (DCEs), the attributes of each medical treatment are assigned different levels that can be combined into profiles, and several profiles are combined into groups of profiles known as choice sets. The profiles and choice sets are determined by an experimental design. Each patient is presented with a series of choice sets and asked to choose their preferred profile in

each choice set. Alternatively, a patient could be asked to rank profiles in a choice set or rate his or her strength of preference for one profile over an alternative profile or to allocate the percentage of patients that would be treated best with each alternative profile in each choice set. The pattern of responses is analysed to estimate the rate at which patients are willing to trade off among the attributes and changes in attribute levels included in the study. The results can provide measures of the relative importance of attributes or changes in attribute levels and the rate of trade-off among attributes or attribute levels. (Bridges et al., 2011; De Bekker-Grob et al, 2012; Lancsar & Louviere, 2008; MDIC 2015).

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. utilities reflecting preference for each level of each attribute) about patient preferences regarding medical products. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between attributes (or its levels) and/or alternatives. Can provide attribute relative importance, willingness to pay, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, uncertainty tolerance, preference heterogeneity and potential uptake rates.

19. Measure of Value

Measure of value is often used within the context of optimal policy decision-making. To identify the optimal bundle of services to be provided given resource constraints, individuals are asked to allocate a fixed amount of resources between different services. These allocations are analysed to identify the trade-offs individuals make (Weinstein et al., 2003). This method differs from allocation of points in a sense that Measure of Value explicitly combines the allocation tasks and identifying the optimum bundle of services.

Main outcome: Quantitative data regarding the trade-offs respondents make when confronted with resource constraints. These trade-offs are relevant to obtain data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

20. Outcome prioritization tool

The outcome prioritization tool (OPT) is a conversation tool. It has movable buttons on a scale of 0–100, each representing health outcomes. The participant needs to prioritize the outcomes from most important to least important according to the “trade off” principle while using a finite amount of points; the participant is informed that choosing one of the outcomes as being more important implied that she or he was willing to compromise on the less important outcomes (Case et al., 2015). This method is closely related to allocation of points. However, the main difference between OPT and allocation of points is that in OPT health outcomes are presented to individuals by making use of a specific tool where individuals are asked to rate health states by moving buttons on a scale to rate health states.

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between outcomes.

21. Person Trade-off

The Person Trade-off (PTO) technique may be seen as an extension to the TTO approach (see 30). Whilst the TTO approach values the health effects of interventions with a time trade-off, the PTO technique forces individuals to choose between the combinations of the two variables that she/he finds to be equivalent using persons as the equilibrating mechanism (i.e., the number of people that may benefit from a health care intervention, and the health improvement to be brought about by the implementation of this health care intervention) (Green, 2001; Nord, 1995).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. Generally used to statistically examine time trade-offs between outcomes allowing for distributive issues.

22. (Probabilistic) Threshold Technique

Threshold techniques determine the maximal change in one attribute respondents are willing to accept to achieve a given change in another attribute (Kopec et al., 2007). Typically, subjects are shown a pair of treatment profiles that differ in two attributes, and then asked which they prefer. One of these attributes is varied until the subject is indifferent between the two profiles. This eventually leads to information about the relative desirability or acceptability of a specific profile.

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. utilities reflecting preference for each level of each attribute) about patient preferences regarding medical products. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between attributes (or its levels) and/or alternatives. Can provide attribute relative importance, willingness to pay, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, uncertainty tolerance, preference heterogeneity and potential uptake rates.

23. Q-methodology

Q-methodology elicits preferences by presenting individuals with a set of statements about the topic of interest and asking them to order these statements based on their opinion (most commonly, the extent to which they agree or disagree with the statements) using a specially designed response grid (Cross, 2005; Exel, Graaf, & Brouwer, 2007).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are overall ranking scores of the individuals.

24. Qualitative Discriminant Process

The qualitative discriminant process (QDP) is a scoring and ranking process technique. The technique is based on decision analysis techniques. This technique involves three steps: 1) ranking scenarios of qualitative descriptions, 2) mapping the qualitative outcomes to a numeric scale and 3) using statistical techniques to identify preferences and solving a maximization problem within given constraints (Mullen, 1999).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices by asking respondents about their opinions regarding specific qualitative categories, point estimates, and a maximization problem within given resource constraints.

25. Repertory Grid Method

The repertory grid method (RGM) is a method for eliciting personal constructs, i.e. what people think about a given topic. As a method, it can be used to elicit personal constructs by asking individuals to identify overlapping dimensions (i.e., criteria, elements etc.) between alternatives. The task is stopped when individuals are unable to identify overlapping dimensions between alternatives and the construct is completed. After completion of the construct individuals are asked to rate these dimensions on a scale. In this way the dimensions are rated and the underlying aspect that the respondent uses to rate the dimensions is the construct. One of the strengths of RGM as described in the literature is that it allows the elicitation of perceptions without researcher bias or interference. (Davis, Fuller, Tremblay, & Berndt, 2006; Rowe et al., 2005).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices by asking respondents about overlapping dimensions between alternatives.

26. Self-explicated conjoint

Self-explicated conjoint is a type of conjoint analysis that focuses on the evaluation of various attributes of a product. This conjoint analysis model explicitly asks individuals about the preference for each attribute level rather than the preference for a bundle of attributes. Although the approach is different, the outcome is the same compared to traditional conjoint analysis (Riquelme & Rickards, 1992).

Main outcome: Quantitative data (e.g. utilities reflecting preference for each level of each attribute) about patient preferences regarding medical products. Generally used to statistically examine trade-offs between attributes (or its levels) and/or alternatives. Can provide attribute relative importance, willingness to pay, maximum acceptable risk, minimum required benefit, uncertainty tolerance, preference heterogeneity and potential uptake rates.

27. Standard Gamble

Standard gamble (SG) is a stated-preference approach in which patients are asked to choose between a certain outcome and a gamble between two uncertain outcomes, each with a probability of occurrence and where their aggregate chance of occurrence is 100%. Typically, the certain outcome is described as a health state, defined by individual attributes or by profiles. The two outcomes in the gamble are death and perfect health. The probabilities of death and perfect health are varied until the patient is indifferent between the certain outcome and the gamble between death and perfect health. The probability of perfect health at which the patient is indifferent between the

certain outcome and the gamble is the health-state utility. SG also can be used to elicit risk tolerance directly. One minus the health utility can be interpreted as the maximum risk of death that would be tolerated in exchange for an improvement from experiencing the outcome to perfect health (i.e., elimination of the outcome or outcomes that define the health state) (Gafni, 1994; MDIC, 2015; Morimoto & Fukui, 2002).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are health state utilities.

28. Starting Known Efficacy

Starting known efficacy (SKE) is a specific variant of threshold technique (see 21) mostly used within pharmaceutical sciences. It differs from the threshold technique in that the threshold identification starts with a specific known starting point. The traditional threshold technique often starts with extreme values on both ends of the scale (Man-Son-Hing et al., 1996).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about the maximal risk respondents are willing to take to achieve a specific health benefit. Can be used to obtain patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices.

29. Swing Weighting

Swing weighting is a method for setting the weights typically used in an additive multi-attribute utility function. Swing weighting requires that each attribute in a set be assigned a range of minimum to maximum levels, such that the full range of theoretically or decision-relevant levels is included within the range. The attributes are then ranked in decreasing order of the importance that a change in each attribute, from its lowest level to its highest level, would have on a given decision. The attribute with the highest rank is assigned a weight of 100. The second attribute is then assigned a weight on a scale from 1 to 100, reflecting the degree a swing from its lowest to highest level would influence the decision, compared with the highest-ranked feature. Thus, higher weights indicate greater importance. This process is repeated for all attributes. The resulting weights are normalized to sum 100 and provide a weight for each attribute over the range of levels assigned to that feature providing information about the relative desirability or acceptability of an attribute. (MDIC, 2015; Ryan et al., 2014).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices by identifying weights for different attributes and/or outcomes to determine utilities.

30. Test Trade-off

The test trade-off method within medical risk prediction modelling was introduced to evaluate a new biomarker (attachment used to indicate an effect) at a specified risk threshold. The test tradeoff corresponding to a risk threshold is the minimum number of tests for a new biomarker that one is

willing to trade for a true positive to yield an increase in the net benefit of risk prediction with the additional biomarker. The test tradeoff can then be considered in light of any detrimental side effects or monetary costs of testing for the biomarker. In other words: this method can be used to uncover the level of test sensitivity that offsets the costs or side effects of a test. For example a test tradeoff of 100 tests could be reasonable if the test involves only a simple blood test but unreasonable if the test requires an invasive biopsy. Computation of the test tradeoff at various risk thresholds provides a sensitivity analysis (Stuart G. Baker & Kramer, 2014; S. G. Baker, Van Calster, & Steyerberg, 2012).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are trade-offs between different tests.

31. Time Trade-off

Time trade-off is a stated-preference approach in which patients are asked to choose between living a specified time in a specified state of health and a shorter time in perfect health. Health states can be defined by individual attributes or by profiles. The time spent in perfect health then is varied until the patient is indifferent between longer life in the worse health state and the shorter life in perfect health. The ratio of the shorter amount of time in perfect health to the longer amount of time in the health state is the health-state utility. Higher values indicate greater preference for the health state. (Arnesen & Trommald, 2005; Brazier, Deverill, & Green, 1999; MDIC 2015).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally preferences regarding health states.

32. Visual Analogue Scale

The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) is a self-reporting device consisting of a line of predetermined length that separates extreme boundaries of the phenomenon being measured. When using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) respondents are presented with a line with anchors at best imaginable health-state (with a score of 100) and worst imaginable health-state (with a score of 0). Such applications have often provided guidance to respondents by providing numbers at intervals. Respondents are then asked to indicate on this scale the point corresponding to either their own health-state, or another defined health-state (Holdgate et al., 2003; Räsänen et al., 2006).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally values of health states.

Scale related techniques (i.e. no preference assessment methods!)

A. Guttman scales

Guttman scales are generally used to assess preferences. To assess preferences respondents are asked to respond to statements in terms of 'agree' or 'disagree' to identify trade-offs (Panchapakesan, Klassen, Cano, Scott, & Pusic, 2013; Sossong, Felder, Wolff, & Krüger, 2016).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. Generally used to statistically determine trade-offs.

B. Juster's 11 point probability scale

Juster's 11 point probability scale can be used to produce estimates of the average probability that a population will do something by a future time. Since what is being measured is a probability, the mean response estimates the proportion of the population that will perform the behavior at issue. An example is given by the question, 'On a scale of 0 - 10 where 0 indicates no chance and 10 indicates certainty, what is the chance that you will change your primary bank in the next 12 months?' If then the average response is 3.2, this translates to 32 per cent of the population intend to switch banks (Janet, Philip, & Jordan, 2011; Uncles & Lee, 2006).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally average probabilities.

C. Likert scales

This technique elicits respondents' attitudes by presenting them with a series of outcomes and asking them to rate these outcomes on this scale. The scale (five or seven point scale) for example might look like "very bad", "bad", "mildly bad", "neutral", "mildly good", "good", "very good". (Meenan Rf Fau - Gertman, Gertman Pm Fau - Mason, & Mason, 1980; Norman, 2010).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally scores.

D. Semantic Differential Technique

Using the semantic differential technique (SDT), attitudes are elicited according to a number of opposite or polar adjectives at each end of a scale. Responses are subsequently scored to give an overall 'attitude score (Norbergh, Helin, Dahl, Hellzén, & Asplund, 2006).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally scores.

E. Verbal Numeric Scale

Verbal Numeric Scale (VNS) is a technique identical to the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) (see 37),

but explicitly verbally conducted (Bailey, Daoust, Doyon-Trottier, Dauphin-Pierre, & Gravel, 2010; Holdgate, Asha, Craig, & Thompson, 2003).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally values of health states.

Decision-making frameworks (i.e. no preference assessment methods!)

I. MACBETH

MACBETH stands for ‘Measuring Attractiveness by a Categorical Based Evaluation Technique’. It is a value measurement approach that uses nonnumerical judgements about the difference of attractiveness in pairwise comparisons to gain scores for options and weights for criteria in MCDA (Rodrigues, 2014).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally scores and weights for MCDA.

II. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, or MCDA, is a framework that can be applied to complex decisions. It is most applicable to solving problems that are characterized as a choice among alternatives. It is claimed to help subjects focus on what is important, is logical and consistent, and is easy to use. When used for group decision making, MCDA helps groups discuss their decision opportunity (the problem to be solved) in a way that allows them to consider the values that each group member views as important. It provides an ability for people to consider and talk about complex trade-offs among alternatives. It is claimed to help people think, re-think, query, adjust, decide, rethink some more, test, adjust, and finally decide. More specifically, this framework is used to assess the performance of different alternatives, to obtain the relative importance weights (for example through DCE or AHP) of these alternatives and to eventually combine performance scores and weights into an overall assessment for each alternative (Marsh et al., 2016; Thokala et al., 2016). In a typical MCDA, the steps are to identify an hierarchy of objectives to be met or maximized by the alternative (treatments), develop measurement scales for those objectives which serve as inputs (akin to attributes) to the model; develop “value functions” that convert each measurement into a normalized scale, assign weights to each input and for objectives at higher levels in the hierarchy, score the inputs for each alternative (treatment) being considered, develop total weighted scores for each alternative using the model, then compare the weighted scores and components scores so as to understand the ranking of alternatives. Sensitivity analyses on the weights can give greater confidence in the results.

Main outcome: Qualitative and quantitative data about ranking and choice of medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally a combination of scores and weights for different

alternatives.

III. Relative value adjusted NNT and NNH

The number needed to treat (NNT) is an epidemiological measure used in communicating the effectiveness of a health-care intervention, typically a treatment with medication. The NNT is the average number of patients who need to be treated to prevent one additional harmful outcome (e.g. the number of patients that need to be treated for one of them to benefit compared with a control in a clinical trial). It is defined as the inverse of the absolute risk reduction. The larger the NNT, the less effective is the treatment. Related to NNT is NNH: number needed to harm. In the simplest form, a decision rule is “if $NNT > NNH$, then the benefits outweigh the harms for the treatment vs. the comparator”. This rule does not account for multiple benefits and harms nor the relative clinical impact, or weight, of each. Relative value adjusted NNT and NNH (RV-NNT and RV-NNH) was developed to take into account both multiple benefits and risks and these weights (Dowie, 1998).

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices by calculating the weight or preference-adjusted number of persons to treat or harm to prevent one additional bad outcome.

IV. Stochastic Multi Criteria Acceptability Analysis

Stochastic Multicriteria Acceptability Analysis (SMAA) is a multiple-criteria decision analysis method for problems with missing or incomplete information. Since criteria and preference information can be uncertain, inaccurate or partially missing. Incomplete information is represented in SMAA using suitable probability distributions. The method is based on stochastic simulation by drawing random values for criteria measurements and weights from their corresponding distributions. SMAA is essentially MCDA when all inputs are assigned probability distributions, and hence, SMAA can handle mixed cardinal and ordinal information. Ordinal information is treated by a special joint distribution that preserves the ordinal information (van Valkenhoef et al., 2012). Typically, results can include the probability the benefits exceed risks and the degree to which each criteria/attribute and its uncertainty contribute to this probability.

Main outcome: Quantitative data about patient preferences regarding medicinal products and medical devices. These data are generally a combination of scores and weights for different alternatives taking into account missing information.

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